

AMERICAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND INNOVATION (AJMRI)

ISSN: 2158-8155 (ONLINE), 2832-4854 (PRINT)

VOLUME 1 ISSUE 5 (2022)

PUBLISHED BY: E-PALLI, DELAWARE, USA

The Mediating Effect of Job Satisfaction on the Relationship Between Work Engagement and Individual Work Performance Among Public School Teachers

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Article Information

Received: November 07, 2022

Accepted: November 20, 2022

Published: November 28, 2022

Keywords

*Educational Management,
Individual Work Performance,
Job Satisfaction, Mediating Effect,
Philippines, Public School Teachers,
Work Engagement*

ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study is to examine the mediation effect of job satisfaction on the relationship between work engagement and individual work performance. The data collected used a survey questionnaire on a sample of 311 public school teachers in the North and South Districts of Kiblawan, Davao del Sur. The researcher administered questionnaires using a 5-point Likert scale. In the statistical analysis, job satisfaction was the mediating variable, work engagement was identified as the independent variable, and individual work performance was the dependent variable. Path Analysis was used to establish the relationships among the variables. Results showed that work engagement and individual work performance are positively correlated, and the connection is significant. Similarly, work engagement and job satisfaction have a positive causal relationship, and the association is also significant. Likewise, job satisfaction and individual work performance also have a significant relationship and are positively correlated. Findings also revealed that job satisfaction partially mediates the relationship between work engagement and individual work performance. Such that 48.8% of the overall influence of work engagement on individual work performance appears to be mediated by job satisfaction. The remaining 51.2% seems to be either direct or mediated by factors not included in the model.

INTRODUCTION

Teachers should inspire students to work hard and assist them in finding a place in today's world where they can blend in. With the overwhelming demands of today's society on youth development, teachers' job performance both within and outside the classroom is critical for all stakeholders, including school administrators, parents, and education policymakers (Alrajhi *et al.*, 2017).

Imparting education to students is based on the teacher's performance. As a result, several variables add to it. The researcher extensively reviewed the literature for its associated variables because of the importance of studies on individual work performance. Work engagement was the first variable considered to be relevant. Work engagement is significantly linked to in-role and extra-role performance (Halbesleben & Wheeler, 2008; Schaufeli, Taris, & Bakker, 2006) and business unit performance (Harter, Schmidt, & Hayes, 2002). According to Beal (2005), "individuals perform better when fully engaged in the task at hand."

Another variable that caught the attention of the researcher is job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is favorable or positive feelings about work or the environment (Furnham, 1997). It can also be explained as the psychological disposition of people toward their work – which involves a collection of numerous attitudes or feelings (Schultz, 1999). However, the researcher would like to know how job satisfaction mediates the effect of work engagement on individual work performance,

In the above context, the researcher took an interest in examining if job satisfaction will mediate the relationship between work engagement and individual work performance, making this study a generation of new

knowledge that can contribute to the field of education. The main thrust of this study was to determine the mediating effect of job satisfaction on the relationship between work engagement and individual work performance among public school teachers in the Davao Region. Specifically, the following objectives are formulated:

1. to describe the level of work engagement of public-school teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. vigor,
 - 1.2. dedication and
 - 1.3. absorption.
2. to ascertain the level of individual work performance of public-school teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1. task performance (TP),
 - 2.2. contextual performance (CP) and
 - 2.3. counterproductive work behavior (CWB).
3. to measure the level of job satisfaction among public school teachers.
4. to determine the significance of the relationship between:
 - 4.1. work engagement and individual work performance;
 - 4.2. work engagement and job satisfaction; and
 - 4.3. job satisfaction and individual work performance leadership.
5. to determine the significance of mediation of job satisfaction on the relationship between work engagement and individual work performance among public school teachers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section presents sufficient evidence to support the research aims, which is critical for the study's expression

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of comprehension. It does this by presenting a variety of approaches, points of view, theories, findings from research and publications, and insightful observations from various authors relevant to related topics of the study. Work engagement is the independent variable, while energy, devotion, and absorption are its markers (Bakker & Demmerouti, 2008). Individual work performance is the dependent variable, and its indications include task performance, contextual performance, and unproductive work behavior (Koopmans *et al.*, 2012).

Finally, the mediating factor is work satisfaction. Work Engagement. Work engagement is strongly associated with an individual's mental perspective in which individuals invest in their physical, intellectual, and enthusiastic assets when performing work. Moreover, representatives depict solid occupation execution in the working environment within sight of three mental conditions identified with significant experience, well-being, and accessibility (Khan, 1990). Moreover, work engagement is beneficial to work inclusion that partners with difficult work with delight in the obligations (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2001).

Fundamentally, work engagement is an amazing development that shows energy, inclusion, and the center among individuals in meeting authoritative objectives and targets (Macey & Schneider, 2008; Schaufeli, Salanova, & Gonzalez, 2002). Additionally, the most recent conceptions of job motivation emphasize the fundamental components of vitality and interest in the workplace (Bakker, Albercht, & Leiter, 2011). It recognizes that commitment is varied from day to day, week to week, and even task to task, not static (Sonnentag, 2011).

Despite the fact that levels of engagement alter over time, involvement is defined as a "generally experienced affective-cognitive state that is not fixated on any one thing, event, individual, or activity." (Schaufeli *et al.*, 2006). Therefore, it may be assessed using static indicators. Furthermore, job motivation is associated with people's psychological experiences, which influence their work process and behavior. Employee engagement is multifaceted; committed workers are mentally, psychologically, and cognitively invested in their everyday jobs (Eldor & Harpaz, 2015).

The organization is responsible for meeting the needs of its workers by delivering appropriate training and creating a meaningful working environment; employees, in exchange, are responsible for making a meaningful contribution to the organization. Many organizations recognize the value of employee engagement; however, the question of how to maximize employee engagement is unwarranted (Wang & Chia-Chun, 2013).

Numerous researchers have acknowledged that job engagement has distinctive characteristics that have a direct positive impact on individual and hierarchical performance. Accordingly, work engagement is firmly identified with a perspective described by vigor, dedication, and absorption (Schaufeli, Pinto, Salanova, & Bakker, 2002). The first indicator is vigor. Vigor is described as "elevated levels of energy and mental

stamina when working, the ability to spend effort in one's job, and perseverance in the face of adversity" (Schaufeli *et al.*, 2002). *Vigor* is an affective construct that calls the subjective sense of energy and aliveness (Shriom, 2004). (Peterson & Seligman, 2004; Ryan & Frederick, 1997). It is also essential for stimulating innovative and constructive interacting activities important to the company (Sonntag & Niessen, 2008).

Furthermore, among the energy dimensions, *vigor* is viewed as the inverse of mental fatigue (Schaufeli *et al.*, 2002). (Gonzalez-Roma *et al.*, 2006; Schaufeli *et al.*, 2002). Low energy levels suggest a high degree of fatigue, while high energy levels indicate a high level of *vigor* (Gonzalez-Roma *et al.*, 2006).

Because of the durability of fundamental work and organizational aspects, research has usually characterized task commitment as a stable variable (Macey & Schneider, 2008). Individuals can, however, have varying amounts of energy at the end of the day (Sonntag & Niessen, 2008). Often a person will leave their office at the end of the day and still be energized. However, on other days, one does not have much patience and may be unsure how to cope with the obligations of family life (Sonntag & Niessen, 2008).

Vigor is needed for participating in organizationally related activities and has been proposed as one of the central aspects of engagement (Gonzalez-Roma *et al.*, 2006; Sonntag & Niessen, 2008). The second indicator is dedication. Dedication is described as "being deeply engaged in one's work and feeling a sense of importance, passion, and challenge" (Bakker & Demerouti, 2008). It is often the opposite of cynicism - a burnout dimension (González-Romá, Schaufeli, Bakker, & Lloret, 2006). As a result, work engagement is the opposite of burnout along two fundamental sub-constructs known as capacity and identity (González-Romá *et al.*, 2006).

Being motivated, passionate, and deeply invested in your work means being dedicated (Rayton & Yalabik, 2014). Additionally, it involves having a sense of purpose in one's work, feeling ecstatic and proud of one's employment, and being motivated and pushed by one's profession (Song *et al.*, 2012). Employees that are dedicated to their work take pride in what they do. Dedicated employees believe that the work they do is significant and contributes to the organization's overall aim. Cynicism is the polar opposite of devotion. (Schaufeli *et al.*, 2002).

People are engaged when they are given meaningful work that demonstrates how important they are to the company. Employees can, as a result, have an impact on those around them. The benefits of intrinsic incentives are also affected by this phenomenon. Meaningful work will increase employee involvement, but this does not guarantee that the employee will be involved. In order for employees to participate, autonomy, intrinsic rewards, and influence are required (Bolman & Deal, 2014).

The last indicator is absorption. Isolation from one's surroundings, intense focus on one's work, and a general lack of conscious awareness of time spent on one's

employment are all symptoms of absorption (Rayton & Yalabik, 2014). Absorption indicates concentration and being engaged in people's jobs, rendering passing time invisible and separating it from the job impossible. Furthermore, having work experience is enjoyable for individuals. However, they do so just for doing it, and paying a high wage for a career is not as important to them as it is for another individual (Hayati *et al.*, 2014).

Individual Work Performance. Individual job performance was defined as procedures or endeavors pertinent to the association's goals (Campbell, 1990). IWP thus emphasizes the behaviors or actions of representatives more than the results of these behaviors. In addition, the person should substantially affect practices, except those required by the environment (Rotundo & Sackett, 2002). Therefore, choosing the IWP's fundamental structure is crucial before evaluating it. Task execution, which may be defined as the capacity with which employees carry out the centrally important or specialized tasks necessary to their work, has traditionally been the primary focus of the IWP construct (Campbell, 1990).

Practices demonstrating task performance usually include information on work quantity and quality, work skills, and occupations (Rotundo & Sackett, 2002; Campbell, 1990). IWP is thought to be a multidimensional concept (Campbell, 1990; Austin & Villanova, 1992). However, its impact on employee behavior has recently received full attention beyond completing the task (Rotundo & Sackett, 2002; Dalal, 2005; Borman & Motowidlo, 1993). Additionally, several tools were developed to evaluate each individual worker's performance (IWP). However, none of the available tools can now assess the relevant aspects of an individual's work performance (Koopmans, 2015).

Furthermore, the available tools were only designed for a certain population (for example, for specific occupations) (Koopmans, 2014). As a result, the existing instruments, which include participants from many professions, cannot be widely implemented or used for research purposes. Additionally, errors in psychometrics were discovered in the available instruments (Appelbaum, Roy, and Gilliland, 2011). Therefore, the Individual Work Performance Questionnaire (IWPQ) is developed to overcome current tools' drawbacks (Koopmans, 2014). Task performance (TP), contextual performance (CP), and counterproductive work behavior are the three metrics that make up the IWP, according to a purposeful audit (Koopmans *et al.*, 2011) and field testing of the IWPQ (Koopmans *et al.*, 2012). (CWB).

The first indicator is task performance (TP). Task performance is the proficiency or ability to execute the job's main or critical tasks (Koopmans *et al.*, 2011). This component includes the capacity to plan and arrange activities, maintain consistency, produce results, and operate efficiently. There are two ways to complete tasks: directly converting raw materials into finished products or indirectly converting raw materials into finished products. The second responsibility includes upkeep

and maintenance tasks for the technical center. Task performance is connected to the organization's technical foundation. Finally, task performance relates to teaching, a group of supervised work tasks that a teacher may do. Instructional effectiveness, teacher-student engagement, and teaching significance are part of how well instructors do their tasks (Cai & Lin, 2006).

The second indicator is contextual performance (CP). Contextual performance can be described as additional actions and activities outside of the critical duties that enable the management, such as performing extra tasks, taking the initiative, taking on complex tasks, and improving knowledge and skills (Koopmans *et al.*, 2011). Contextual performance differs from task performance in that its activities are not included in the job description (Sonnentag *et al.*, 2008). On the other hand, contextual performance implicitly fosters operational performance by fostering task performance. In addition, contextual success improves organizational effectiveness by influencing the psychological, social, and organizational job environments (Motowidlo, 2003).

Individuals participate across contexts in a variety of areas, including (1) encouraging people to be more likely to conduct actions that contribute to organizational success, (2) improving the individual's willingness to contribute to the organization, and (3) demonstrating an activity that influences the organization's capital. The third indicator is counterproductive to work behavior (CWB). CWB applies to cooperative action in which workers are either unmotivated to comply or encouraged to transgress. CWB also implies that the employee is not inclined to adhere and is motivated to behave in opposition to agreed corporate standards.

Theft, deception, sabotage, absenteeism, physical aggression, and verbal aggression are examples of CWB actions. A significant difference between forms of deviance was whether the deviance was aimed or aimed at the organization (organizational deviance) or its participants (interpersonal deviance) (Robinson & Bennett, 1995).

Antisocial behavior, counterproductive behavior, dysfunctional behavior, and corporate misbehavior are all synonyms for CWB (Sackett, 2002; Bennett & Robinson, 2000). CWB may also be a voluntary activity that breaks major organizational standards and endangers its well-being, employees, or both. Possibility explanations are also given by social exchange theory and reciprocity theory. Employees with low morale can use CWB to retaliate against their employees for creating an uncomfortable work environment. Employees with poor employee commitment are unconcerned about losing their work and likely participate in activities that jeopardize their careers.

Job Satisfaction. People's views and feelings toward their jobs are referred to as job satisfaction. Positive and significant attitudes about work indicate job satisfaction. Work unhappiness manifests itself in negative and disgusting attitudes toward employment. (Armstrong,

2006). The range of emotions and convictions people have about their current place of employment is called job satisfaction. People's levels of job satisfaction might range from intense fulfillment to excruciating disappointment. People may have opinions about their employment generally, as well as specific aspects of such roles, such as the type of work they do, their coworkers, superiors, or subordinates, and their salary (George & Jones, 2008).

Additionally, work satisfaction is a confusing and complex concept that means different things to different people. Inspiration and job happiness are frequently linked, although the exact nature of this connection is uncertain. Inspiration and fulfillment are not the same thing. Job satisfaction significantly affects one's attitude and psychological condition. For instance, it could be connected to a person's subjective or objective sense of accomplishment (Mullins, 2005).

Additionally, job satisfaction carries a significant psychological component. It is connected to a sense of personal well-being and productivity, but the latter has yielded inconclusive results. Productivity benefited job satisfaction, and the correlation between job satisfaction and performance could not be proved with certainty. According to the research in the field, job satisfaction is also linked to management. The relationship with management staff is second in classifying the characteristics that determine professional fulfillment (Bruce & Blackburn, 1992).

In addition, the variety of duties and responsibilities is a critical component in determining job satisfaction (Sutter, 1994). In the same way, job satisfaction among teachers is a multifaceted concept that is a significant determinant of teacher motivation and thus a contributor to school effectiveness. Moreover, it is a dynamic variable determined by situational work considerations and the individual's dispositional characteristics. As a result, work satisfaction is an attitude toward one's job that considers one's emotions, values, and behaviors (Munir & Khattoon, 2015).

Teaching is a difficult and demanding profession. To sustain their enthusiasm, passion, and energy for teaching, teachers must remain committed to the profession with which they are normally associated (Day, 2000). The fulfillment instructors feel while teaching and the connection between their needs and preferences are two factors that contribute to their work satisfaction (Zambylas and Papanastasiou 2004). Teachers that are happy with their jobs are more committed to their students and the school. Better enthusiasm and self-efficacy have also been seen in teachers with higher work satisfaction (motivations).

These are crucial factors in determining teachers' well-being, classroom behavior, and the educational, motivational, and emotional results of students (Buric & Moe, 2020). One of the key factors associated with teachers' job satisfaction is their competence and performance as instructors, given the significance of

motivation in improving teachers' performance in the classroom. In addition, teaching satisfaction is determined by the assumed relationship between what one desires from one's work and what one perceives teaching to give or imply. This teaching satisfaction is the end effect of teachers' attitudinal and affective reactions (Ho, Au, 2006). Teachers are delighted that their jobs positively impact achieving instructional goals. Therefore, it is anticipated that a school with teachers who are happy in their jobs would provide qualified education and raise active students. Ahmed, Raheem, and Jamal (2003) assessed 236 secondary school teachers' job satisfaction. When male and female teachers were compared, female teachers were determined to be happier than male teachers. In addition, teachers at public schools reported being more satisfied than those in private schools. According to the research, occupational stress and position of influence on vocational teachers are not different by gender (Gupta & Sahu, 2009).

According to the research, government school instructors who are experienced and married are happier than private school teachers (Agarwal, 2004). However, it was also revealed that work satisfaction was unaffected by age or marital status. Finally, the working conditions influence the quality of life of teachers. Working conditions are defined by teachers having a secure, pleasant, and appreciative working environment, which is critical for the school to deliver high-quality education. Teachers perform better when their work environment is positive and consistent with institutional practice (Ye, 2016).

Good teachers, as previously stated, require a workplace that supports their endeavors in various ways to maintain their effective teaching and accomplish their best job with kids (Berry, Daughtrey & Wieder, 2010). Lack of such, instructors are hesitant to commit to schools because of the adverse effects of inadequate working conditions (Ye, 2016; Ladd, 2009). Teachers who are happy with their jobs will make significant progress by working in a triangle with managers, teachers, and parents. Poor teaching satisfaction is associated with job stress, including relational depression and low self-esteem (Ho & Au, 2006).

Correlation between Variables. Engagement at work is crucial for businesses because it impacts the bottom line (Demerouti & Cropanzano, 2010; Macey & Schneider, 2008). Work engagement is positively correlated with financial results (Xanthopoulou, Bakker, Demerouti, & Schaufeli, 2009), supervisor-rated work performance (Bakker & Bal, 2010; Halbesleben & Wheeler, 2008), and customer happiness (Salanova, Agut, & Peiró, 2005). However, personal and environmental factors can impact the link between job devotion and employee performance. Individual-level personality traits, such as conscientiousness (Demerouti, 2006), have been demonstrated to affect job performance and work engagement.

Moreover, work for engagement benefits staff and organizations when committed workers are likely to do

well (Demerouti & Cropanzano, 2010). Positive feelings such as satisfaction, excitement, and passion account for better success by engaged workers than non-engaged workers (Bakker & Demerouti, 2008). Employees must maintain flow or high commitment to tasks to ensure successful job results. However, high commitment does not always imply good job results.

Work engagement (Bakker, Demerouti & ten Brummelhuis, 2011) and flow experience (Demerouti, 2006) does not increase in-role performance when people are not goal-oriented and diligent. It could be due to their involvement in activities other than the work duties that support the objectives of the business. According to one definition, job satisfaction refers to how employees feel about and enjoy their work. The more satisfied people are with their professions, the more the workplace accommodates their needs and ideals (Abraham, 2012; Papoutsis *et al.*, 2014).

Employee engagement also mediates between HR procedures and employee happiness (Sattar *et al.*, 2015). Furthermore, when leader-member interaction was encouraged, employee engagement and work happiness had a clear link, and job satisfaction acted as a moderator between employee engagement and organizational commitment. (Lee & Ok, 2017).

Employee work performance has long been a significant obstacle in corporate management and implementing successful methods to inspire workers to attain and produce higher job performance. At the same time, organizational productivity is still the primary goal of any company enterprise (Lee & Wu, 2011). However, the declining level of employee performance in organizations is quickly becoming a significant threat to the viability of colleges, which must be resolved immediately. Employee success is thus thought to be essential for organizational development and profitability (Ogbulafor, 2011).

High-performance work systems are directly and indirectly connected to teachers' in-role productivity and extra-role behavior through the mediation of job satisfaction. The relationship between employee work habits and high-performance job performance is mediated by the work-life balance (Shen, J., Benson, J. and Huang, B. 2014). Structural relationships between school culture, self-efficacy, work engagement, and job performance were examined in Korean labor institutions. According to statistics, there was a positive correlation between work engagement and job performance, and instructors' self-efficacy enhanced both variables.

We also identified the moderating roles of self-efficacy and work engagement in the relationships between the school climate in workforce-education institutions and teacher job performance (Shen, J., Benson, J., and Huang, B. 2014). Furthermore, job satisfaction represents the enormity of optimism aligned with real incentives and benefits. Most workers today are dissatisfied with their employment, which leads to unfavorable habits on the job, degrading their success potential and, as a result, their workplace environment (Mowday, Porter & Steers,

2013). Employers' ability to understand staff retention, scheduling, and everyday obligations significantly affect employee productivity and performance. Job satisfaction is a combination of likable and unlikable moods or behavior of an individual working on their work schedule, indicating that when they are working, they may have needs, wishes, and anticipations that determine their reason for being there (Howard, 2009).

Work satisfaction and performance have been studied in various organizational contexts (Judge, Thoresen, Bono & Patton, 2001). The results are, however, often not definitive. For example, few studies have shown associations between work happiness and productivity (Iaffaldano & Muchinsky, 1985; Kohli & Deb, 2008). On the other hand, several research investigations of the literature on job satisfaction have demonstrated a connection between job satisfaction and job performance (Mlyyuka, 2015; Ogundele & Olarewaju, 2014).

The above-related literature pertains to the study's variables: work engagement, individual work performance, and job satisfaction. The findings, readings, and studies included are related to the study. According to the statements, work engagement stresses *vigor, dedication*, and absorption, while individual work performance is measured by task performance, contextual task, and counterproductive work behavior. To sum it up, the cited works were in excessive help to unveil how work engagement, individual work performance, and job satisfaction were related. These would also serve as a support to the study's presentation, results, and findings.

METHODOLOGY

This study used a non-experimental quantitative design with the descriptive correlation research approach to collect data, ideas, facts, and information about the study. Researchers gather data in non-experimental research without modifying or introducing treatments (Gehle, 2013). The factors in this study were not changed, and the environment was not controlled. The descriptive-correlation research design explains and analyzes what it is, revealing existing and non-existing circumstances and relationships (Calderon, 2006; Calmorin, 2007). Furthermore, it is a fact-finding study that allows the researcher to analyze the study participants' features, actions, and experiences (Calmorin, 2007).

The descriptive study assessed school heads' transcendental leadership, accountability climate, and institutional productivity in Kiblawan North and South District public elementary schools. This study is correlational since it investigated the relationship between work engagement, individual work performance, and job satisfaction, using the survey questionnaire to gather the primary data. The interest of the study is to investigate the relationship between work engagement and individual work performance; the relationship between work engagement and job satisfaction; the relationship between job satisfaction and individual work performance; and the mediating effect of job satisfaction on the relationship

between work engagement of public-school teachers and individual work performance of public school teachers in Kiblawan North and South District. Medgraph was employed in determining the mediation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Work Engagement

Shown in Table 1 is the level of Work Engagement. The standard deviation was less than 1.00, which means there is a consistency of responses among respondents. The overall mean score was 4.27 (SD = 0.43), labeled as very high. Teachers’ level of work engagement on the following indicators was as follows: *vigor* has a mean score of 4.22 (SD=0.50), described as very high, *dedication* has a mean score of 4.50 (SD=0.46) with a descriptive level of very high, and *absorption*, obtained a mean score of 4.08 (SD=0.57), was labeled as high. The data revealed that the teachers as leaders had a very good command of work engagement in terms of *vigor*, indicating that teachers put energy, effort, and enthusiasm into their work to attain authoritative aims and goals. Also, the data showed that work engagement in *dedication* is always manifested.

Table 1: Level of Work Engagement

Indicators	\bar{x}	SD	Descriptive Level
Vigor	4.22	0.50	Very High
Dedication	4.50	0.46	Very High
Absorption	4.08	0.57	High
Overall	4.27	0.43	Very High

This result indicates the respondents’ *very high* involvement in the task given; they are enthusiastic and proud of doing the job. Lastly, teachers’ level of work engagement in *absorption* was high, which indicates that the respondents are highly focused and absorbed in their work, not minding the amount of time they are involved in the task.

Level of Individual Work Performance

The Individual Work Performance is analyzed using three (3) indicators. The indicator Task Performance obtained a mean score of 4.34 (SD=0.50), while Contextual Performance obtained a mean score of 4.24 (SD=0.49), and the *Counterproductive Performance* obtained a mean score of 2.34 (SD=1.08). Furthermore, the table shows an overall mean score of 3.64 (SD=0.48), which indicates that individual work performance is evident most of the time to the respondents. The result shows that the Level of Individual Work Performance for two indicators, Task Performance, and *Contextual Performance*, with a descriptive level of Very High, are performed at all times.

This result suggests that the respondents show a proficient ability to execute and are capable of performing additional activities and taking initiatives to improve their knowledge at all times. In contrast, *Counterproductive Performance* with a descriptive level of Low indicates that the teachers are highly driven and are not likely to misbehave.

Also, the level of organizational culture in terms of

Table 2: Level of Individual Work Performance

Indicators	\bar{x}	SD	Descriptive Level
Task Performance	4.34	0.50	Very High
Contextual Performance	4.24	0.49	Very High
Counterproductive Performance	2.34	1.08	Low
Overall	3.64	0.48	High

contextual performance was very high, indicating that teachers can perform extra tasks, take the initiative, take on difficult tasks, and improve knowledge and skills. Lastly, the data revealed that the respondents’ level of individual work performance in *counterproductive* performance was low. It showed that the teachers are highly driven and are not likely to misbehave.

Level of Job Satisfaction

Shown in Table 3 is the level of job satisfaction of public elementary school teachers in Davao del Sur. The overall mean score was 3.56 (SD= 0.41), described as high. The result implies that job satisfaction is manifested or felt most of the time. Particularly, the level of job satisfaction on the following items was as follows:

Teachers leading vocationally unsatisfied lives have a mean score of 2.37 (SD=1.24) in which the descriptive level is low; people giving me much respect when they know that I am a teacher has a mean score of 3.98 (SD=0.81) which means high; perhaps being better if I had joined some other profession has a mean score of 3.16 (SD=1.22) which means moderate; having a salary in teaching job is not keeping with my abilities and qualification has a mean score of 2.87 (SD=1.21) which means moderate; giving fresh opportunity for choosing a career, I will again, be choosing teaching has a mean of 4.05 (SD=0.99) which means high; believing that no profession is as good as teaching has a mean of 3.86 (SD=1.15) which means high, believing that teaching is boring because of repetition of similar work has a mean of 2.24 (SD=1.21) which means low, believing that the work of teachers is interesting because of variety of activities has a mean of 4.28 (SD=0.78) which means very high, believing that society appreciates teacher’s work has a mean of 4.02 (SD=0.87) which means high, believing that the teaching profession is one among the few noble professions has a mean of 4.50 (SD=0.74) which means very high, teaching profession is providing opportunities for satisfaction of my abilities and capacities has a mean of 4.38 (SD=0.68) which means very high, believing that economic condition of a teacher makes me dislike this profession has a mean of 2.72 (SD=1.27) which means moderate, controlling student is headache for me has a mean of 2.82 (SD=1.20) which means moderate, believing that kind treatment of teachers spoils the students has a mean of 3.29 (SD=1.1) which means moderate, being interested to attend seminars within

and outside the school has a mean of 4.17 (SD=0.73) which means high, having school authorities who are fair and impartial has a mean of 3.81 (SD=0.88) which means high, having teacher colleagues who are good and cooperative has a mean of 4.33 (SD=0.74) which means very high, always keeping track of my progress has a mean of 4.22 (SD=0.69) which means very high, sometimes feeling my job is meaningless has a mean of 2.21 (SD=1.22) which means low, and being satisfied with

my chances of promotion has a mean of 3.96 (SD=0.84) which means high. It can be inferred that the respondents have high views about the teaching profession and see that educators are important assets to society. Also, teachers believe that being in the profession of teaching provides growth opportunities. Moreover, it can be gleaned that having a good working environment will lead to a high motivation to perform proficiently. Furthermore, it can be inferred that appropriate review,

Table 3: Level of Job Satisfaction

Items	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Teachers are leading vocationally unsatisfied lives.	2.37	1.24	Low
People give me much respect when they know that I am a teacher.	3.98	0.81	High
Perhaps being better if I had joined some other profession.	3.16	1.22	Moderate
Having a salary in a teaching job is not in keeping with my abilities and qualification.	2.87	1.21	Moderate
Given a fresh opportunity for choosing a career, I will again be choosing teaching.	4.05	0.99	High
Believing that no profession is as good as teaching.	3.86	1.15	High
Believe that teaching is boring because of the repetition of similar work.	2.24	1.21	Low
Believing that the work of teachers is interesting because of the variety of activities.	4.28	0.78	Very High
Believing that society appreciates teachers' work.	4.02	0.87	High
Believing that the teaching profession is one of the few noble professions.	4.50	0.74	Very High
The teaching profession provides opportunities for the satisfaction of my abilities and capacities.	4.38	0.68	Very High
Believing that the economic condition of a teacher makes me dislike this profession.	2.72	1.27	Moderate
Controlling students is a headache for me.	2.82	1.20	Moderate
Believing that kind of treatment of teachers spoils the students.	3.29	1.11	Moderate
Being interested in attending seminars within and outside the school.	4.17	0.73	High
Having school authorities who are fair and impartial.	3.81	0.88	High
Having teacher colleagues who are good and cooperative.	4.33	0.74	Very High
Always keeping track of my progress.	4.22	0.69	Very High
Sometimes feeling my job is meaningless.	2.21	1.22	Low
Being satisfied with my chances of promotion.	3.96	0.84	High
Overall	3.56	0.41	High

monitoring, and evaluation processes are evident. The teachers can recognize their impact on group dynamics, thus, establishing effective working relationships with other schoolteachers, parents, and community members. Correlations Between Work Engagement and Job Satisfaction Reflected in Table 4 were the test results on the relationship between work engagement and job satisfaction. As shown in Table 4, the indicators of work engagement are positively correlated to job satisfaction. The result shows an overall r-value of .438 with a p-value

of <0.05, thus, signifying the rejection of the null hypothesis. It means a significant relationship between job satisfaction and work engagement. Distinctively, the result reveals that all indicators of work engagement are positively correlated to job satisfaction since the p-value is <0.05 and the overall r-value is .366 for *vigor*, 0.262 for *dedication*, and 0.470 for *absorption*. Data shows the positive association between the two variables.

Table 4: Significance of the Relationship between the Work Engagement and Job Satisfaction

Work Engagement	Job Satisfaction Overall
<i>Vigor</i>	0.366* (0.000)
<i>Dedication</i>	0.262* (0.000)
Absorption	0.470* (0.000)
Overall	0.438* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

Correlations between Job Satisfaction and Individual Work Performance

Shown in Table 5 were the test results on the relationship between individual work performance and job satisfaction. As indicated in the hypothesis, the relationship was tested at a 0.05 level of significance. In the indicator task performance, data shows that it is positively correlated with job satisfaction.

The r-value is 0.388 with a p-value of <0.05. This result shows that task performance is a large part of job satisfaction. Being satisfied in a job requires an ability

to do proficiently at the given task. Likewise, the other contextual performance indicator has an r-value of 0.426 with a p-value of <0.05. The result shows that contextual performance is positively associated with job satisfaction. Furthermore, the result implies that taking the initiative in the tasks is a big part of achieving teachers' job satisfaction. Lastly, the *counterproductive* performance also positively correlated to job satisfaction with an r-value of 0.487 with a p-value of <0.05. This further means that *counterproductive* performance showed a high relationship with job satisfaction.

Table 5: Significance of the Relationship between the Job Satisfaction and Individual Work Performance

Job Satisfaction	Individual Work Performance			
	Task Performance	Contextual Performance	Counterproductive Performance	Overall
Overall	0.388* (0.000)	0.426* (0.000)	0.487* (0.000)	0.646* (0.000)

**Significant at 0.05 significance level.*

The overall result reflects that organizational culture positively correlates to job satisfaction with an overall r-value of 0.646 with a p-value of <0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between individual work performance and job satisfaction, is rejected.

Correlations between Work Engagement and Individual Work Performance

Displayed in Table 6 were the test results of the relationship between work engagement and individual work performance. Reflected in the hypothesis, the

relationship was tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The overall r-value of 0.516 with a p-value of <0.05 signified the rejection of the null hypothesis. It means a significant relationship between transformational leadership and organizational culture. This result implies that the teachers' work engagement is correlated with individual work performance. Results reveal that all work engagement indicators positively correlate to organizational culture since the p-value is <0.05.

The overall r-value is 0.432 for *vigor*, 0.354 for *dedication*, and .234 for *absorption*. Data shows the positive association between the two variables.

Table 6: Significance of the Relationship between the Work Engagement and Individual Work Performance

Work Engagement	Individual Work Performance			
	Task Performance	Contextual Performance	Counterproductive Performance	Overall
Vigor	0.680*(0.000)	0.701*(0.000)	-0.056(0.327)	0.432*(0.000)
Dedication	0.669*(0.000)	0.655*(0.000)	-0.134*(0.018)	0.354*(0.000)
Absorption	0.555*(0.000)	0.642*(0.000)	0.140*(0.013)	0.516*(0.000)
Overall	0.739*(0.000)	0.780*(0.000)	-0.007(0.904)	0.516*(0.000)

**Significant at 0.05 significance level.*

Specifically, in the *counterproductive* performance indicator, data show a low positive correlation with job satisfaction because its computed r-value is close to zero, which is -.007 with a p-value of >0.05. The p-value result means that there is no relationship between the respondents' counterproductive work engagement and individual work performance; individual work performance does not need counterproductive measures in work engagement. Nevertheless, the other indicator, task performance, has an r-value of .739 with a p-value <0.05. This result shows that task performance is positively associated with individual work performance. Lastly, contextual performance got an r-value of .780 with a p-value <0.05, which shows that contextual performance is necessary for individual work performance.

On the Mediating Effect of Job Satisfaction

Shown in Table 7 is the path analysis of the mediating effect of job satisfaction on the relationship between work engagement and individual work performance. The data obtained in this table were results after conducting the SPSS AMOS.

This table presents the direct effect of work engagement on job satisfaction, job satisfaction on individual work performance, and work engagement on individual work performance. Work Engagement and Job Satisfaction is the path a coefficient with an unstandardized regression coefficient of 0.418, standardized regression coefficient of 0.438, SE of 0.049, and a probability value less than 0.05. Below the significance level of 0.05 implies that these two variables have a significant relationship. A

Table 7: Mediating Effect: Path Analysis (Partial Mediation)

Path	Estimates		SE	CR.	P
	Unstandardized	Standardized			
WE- JS	0.418	0.438	0.049	8.596	***
JS - IWP	0.598	0.519	0.052	11.473	***
WE-IWP	0.317	0.289	0.050	6.378	***

low or small standard error means that the estimate is more precise than a higher standard error. Besides, the effect size or the impact of work engagement on job satisfaction is 42%, which completely disavows the null hypothesis. Furthermore, the Path B relationship between Job Satisfaction and Individual Work Performance analysis shows an unstandardized regression coefficient of 0.598, a standardized regression coefficient of 0.519, an SE of 0.052, and a p-value less than 0.05. This result implies a strong relationship between the two variables. Therefore, we can conclude that Job Satisfaction and Individual Work Performance have a significant relationship. Moreover, the effect size of job satisfaction on organizational culture is 60%. And lastly, the path c coefficient shows the effect size of work engagement on individual work performance. The data result has an unstandardized regression coefficient of 0.317 or 32% efficacy, a standardized regression coefficient of .289; the computed standard error is 0.050, and a p-value less than 0.05, which shows a significant relationship between the in. This result supports the assumption that work engagement is associated with individual work performance. In addition, Figure 2 depicts the result of the mediating effect computation. It shows the effect size of path correlation coefficients of the three variables used in this study. At the 0.05 level, the route analysis gave a p-value of less than 0.05, which is significant.

X =WORK ENGAGEMENT (WE)

Y = INDIVIDUAL WORK PERFORMANCE (IWP)

M = JOB SATISFACTION (JS)

Figure 2: The Mediating Effect of Job Satisfaction on the Relationship between Work Engagement and Individual Work Performance

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the study’s findings, the following conclusions are drawn. First, there is compelling evidence that the null hypotheses should be rejected in favor of the alternative hypotheses. Furthermore, respondent public school teachers reported high levels of work engagement, individual work performance, and job satisfaction. The study also discovered a high link between work engagement and individual work performance among public school teachers. Similarly, there is a link between work engagement and job satisfaction. Furthermore, there is a high correlation between job satisfaction and individual job performance.

Lastly, the study’s findings imply that job satisfaction influences and partially mediates the relationship between work engagement and individual work performance. Rather than a straightforward cause-and-effect relationship between work engagement and individual work performance, the findings demonstrated that the former influences job satisfaction, which affects the latter.

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